

INTEGRATED DIAGNOSTIC APPROACHES AND TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS IN PATIENTS WITH INFECTIOUS PATHOLOGIES OF THE GENITOURINARY SYSTEM

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Abstract – Today everyone knows that staphylococcus aureus, streptococcus, staphylococcus are factors of development of chronic relapsing aphthous stomatitis (CRAS) adenoviruses, HIV infection, allergies, immune and autoimmune disorders, diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, liver, pancreas, celiac disease, neuro-trophic factors disorders, genetic predisposition, occupational and industrial hazards [2, 7]. In the pathogenesis and course of CRAS, 3 periods are distinguished: prodromal in the form of mild, moderate and severe severity; period of extinction of the disease [1, 3].

Key words: Oral cavity, urogenital system, immunofluorescence, immunoenzyme, chronic renal failure, conditionally pathogenic pathogens, interleins.

I. Introduction

According to ICD-10, the above pathology is divided into the following: K12 - Stomatitis; K12.0 - Recurrent aphthae in the oral cavity (OC); K12.1 - Other forms of stomatitis (Stomatitis: NOS, ulcerative, dentition, vesicular); K12.2 - Phlegmon and abscess of the mouth. Oral fiber inflammation (OF) and submandibular abscess.

Clinical classification of CRAS proposed by I.M. Rabinovich as fibrinous; necrotic; glandular and deforming forms[8]. Other authors [14] propose to consider the manifestations of CRAS, based on the clinical and morphological patterns of development of the pathological process, and put together 6 forms of CRAS; 1. ulcerative (scarring) form - Setten's afta; 2. A typical form is the Mikulich afta; 3. deforming form; 4. fibrinous form; 5. lichenoid form; and 6. glandular form. [10]

Diagnosis of CRAS is based on anamnesis data: complaints, data on the development of the disease, anamnesis of life, objective examination; clinical picture; the results of a cytological study of scraping from the surface of the ulcer and the detection of a high titer of antibodies to the herpes simplex virus and cytomegalovirus [12, 13].

II. Literature review

The dentist's task is to determine the severity and identify the nature of disorders in the pathology of the digestive system [3, 12] and in the diagnosis of CRAS, various methods can be used as immunohistochemical [9], biochemical and reaction methods of Wasserman, Kahn, Sachs-Vitebsky according to indications.

For the treatment of CRAS, a number of authors suggest the treatment of concomitant diseases, infectious allergies, vitamin deficiencies and at the same time special attention should be paid to identifying local factors, dental diseases and their treatment [10,11], including professional OF hygiene, while irrigation can be carried out OF warm solutions of antiseptics; removal of dental deposits [15]; cleansing the back of the tongue, restores chewing function with artificial orthopedic designs and others.

The aim of the study was to substantiate the effectiveness of diagnostic methods, and the comprehensive treatment of CRAS in infectious inflammatory pathologies of chronic kidney disease and the genitourinary system.

III. Analysis

We have studied 180 patients aged 25 to 45 years, suffering from CRAS (mild to moderate) SOPR of them 120 against the background of chronic inflammatory pathologies of the kidneys and genitourinary system; in order

to assess the effectiveness of the treatment measure of these groups, the patient group was divided into 60 patients (1st primary and 1st comparative groups); and 60 patients suffering from CRAS without chronic inflammatory pathologies of the kidneys and urinary system (group 2) and 20 patients with practical, health as a control.

- I main group, in which antihistamines, sedatives, multivitamin preparations and polyoxidonium (an immunostimulant) were included in the general treatment, in the local phytotherapy rinse treatment at the OF with "Parsley juices" and "Clove essential oil" [4, 5].

- I comparative group, in which the general treatment regimen included antihistamines, sedatives, multivitamin preparations and for local treatment of aphthous elements in the OF put a cotton swab dipped in "aloe vera oil" (*Aloe barbadensis*) [5, 6].

- Group II, where the general treatment included the appointment and inside softened root "Ginger"; every morning one teaspoon per 100 g. a glass of water and Salcoseryl ointment (60 patients).

All clinical information; Dental and urological status was entered in the form No. 043 / of the medical records of the dental patient and in a specially designed chart describing the symptoms of pathologies of the genitourinary system and kidneys. All pathology was diagnosed by ICD-10.

The examined groups underwent clinical and dental research; assessment of the hygienic state of OF (J.C. Green, J.R. Vermillion, 1964); assessment and determination of tooth caries intensity (KPU and PEC); determination of the complex periodontal index ((KPI) to P.A. Leusu 1988), the salivary viscosity was determined (N.V. Gracheva, 1999), and SOPR was examined using a macroluminescent lamp.

In enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and direct immunofluorescence (DIF) reactions studied epithelial cells from the urogenital tract, blood and RG.

General and local immune status were assessed; by the total number and phagocytic activity of leukocytes; (J. Wibran, Y. Funderberg (1973)) and was determined by IgA, IgM, IgG (Mancini G. et al., (1965)) in the saliva and serum blood of the examined. Using biochemical methods, glucose, total protein and their fractions in blood serum and saliva were studied by generally accepted methods.

To process the obtained results, statistical processing was performed on a computer with the use of Microsoft Office (Excel) application programs, a package of statistical programs "Statgraphics v.7", "Stadia" and "Statistica 7.0".

According to pathologies of OF in 120 examined (1st group), it was found - KPU decompensated - 0; KPU, subcompensated form - 1 (0.8%); KPU, compensated form - 3 (2.5%); partial tooth loss - 48 (40.0%); malocclusion pathology - 29 (24.1%); pathological abrasion - 13 (10.8%); local hypoplasia - 2 (1.6%); wedge-shaped defect - 44 (36.6%); periodontal disease - 9 (7.5%); catarrhal gingivitis 38 (31.6%); hypertrophic form of gingivitis 13 (10.8%); periodontitis - 33 (27.5%); swelling of SOPR - 8 (6.6%); dryness, atrophy of SOPR - 5 (4.1%); exfoliative cheilitis - 2 (1.6%); meteorological cheilitis - 9 (7.5%); folded tongue - 6 (5.0%); desquamative glossitis - 5 (4.1%); traumatic erosion - 2 (1.6%); leukoplakia flat - 7 (5.8%); mild leukoplakia - 7 (5.8%); chronic lip crack - 9 (7.5%); lichen planus, typical form - 8 (6.6%); lichen planus, exudative-hypermerized form - 8 (6.6%); herpes - 14 (11.7%); CRAS, Mikulich aphthosis - 90 (75%) and CRAS, Setten aphthosis - 30 (25%). The state of OF in the examined 60 patients (group 2), with CRAS without pathology of chronic renal failure is noted; 0; 0; 1 (1.6%); 25 (41.6%); 15 (25%); 5 (8.3%); 1 (1.6%); 18 (30%); 3 (5.0%); 14 (23.3%); 12 (20.0%); 15 (25.0%); 1 (1.6%); 1 (1.6%); 1 (1.6%); 8 (13.3%); 3 (5.0%); 1 (1.6%); 5 (8.3%); 4 (6.6%); 3 (5.0%); 8 (13.3%); 4 (6.6%); 5 (8.3%); 6 (10%); 0; 0, the examined control group 0; 0; 0; 3 (15%); 2 (10%); 2 (10%); fifteen%; 2 (10%); 1 (5.0%); 3 (15%); 3 (15%); 4 (20%); 0; 0; 0; 2 (10%); 3 (5.0%); fifteen%; 0; 0; 0; (other pathology was not observed), respectively. All examined patients (except the control one) have complaints of discomfort, pain during eating and talking, the presence of "ulcers" in the OF - 76%, dryness in the OF - 7%, and of course the intensity of the pain syndrome depended mainly on the number of elements lesions and localization. In 66% of patients, swelling of the SOPR was detected; 19% of patients noted increased salivation, about 5% - dryness of SOPR. According to the localization of the aphtha in SOPR, in 48% of cases, there is a transitional fold, in 29% on the lateral surface of the tongue, in 12% on the upper and lower lips, in 7% on the cheeks, 2% on the bottom of the palate, in 1% - in the SO of the retromolar region and in 1% - in the SO of the soft palate; as well as in 59% of cases, the elements of the lesion were localized simultaneously in several sections of the SOPR.

As a result of the study, the intensity of dental caries in patients in the 1st group according to the KPI index was 14.61 ± 0.8 ; OHI-S - 1.96 ± 0.06 ; KPI 1.68 ± 0.1 : on the 2nd group, the KPU was - 11.48 ± 0.6 ; OHI-S index - 2.6 ± 0.08 ; KPI - amounted to 1.42 ± 0.2 , in the control group KPU 8.8 ± 0.8 ; OHI-S Index 1.0 ± 0 , 4; KPI 1.0 ± 0.2 .

In patients of the 1st group, a case was observed in 120 patients; concern in connection with the detection of the causative agent of genitourinary infection - 120; increased emotionality - 45; itching, burning in the urogenital tract: constantly - 9; periodically - 6; as a result of cooling, -45; dysuric symptoms - 20; discharge from the urethra and genital organs -2; pain (constantly -5; sometimes, periodically - 55; spontaneous - 51; joint pain -12); symptoms of asthenia, fatigue and malaise - 13; pustular processes on the skin - 30; allergy -62 cases.

After being used by complex, treatment methods for 12-15 days in patients, the 1st group with CRAS on the background of CKD and chronic infection of the genitourinary system showed positive results; anxiety due to the causative agent of genitourinary infection - 10; increased emotionality - 3; itching, burning in the urogenital tract: constantly - 1; periodically - 0; as a result of cooling - 2; dysuric symptoms - 2; painful sensations in total - 5; pustular processes on the skin - 5; allergies - 23.

The dynamics of patients' complaints is directly related to the processes of epithelialization of the elements of the lesion on SOPR in patients of the 1st main group by 7.7 ± 1.2 days; 1st comparative group 10.1 ± 1.4 days; Group 2 8.2 ± 1.1 days of observation showed complete epithelization of aphthae. In particular, the hygienic state of OF was improved in all examined groups due to concurrently reorganized OF.

Most often, blood is used to detect the causative agents of the genitourinary system, as well as scrapings and swabs taken from the genitourinary tract and we know that the composition of blood and saliva is quite closely related to each other. Therefore, the study was carried out on the basis of the presence of CRAS and infections with a tendency to a chronic and recurrent course: mycoplasmosis, chlamydia, and ureaplasmosis, and also studied the indicators of changes in local immunity of OC in the examined before and after treatment.

IV. Discussion

The results of analyzes of some immunological as well as biochemical parameters of pancreatic cancer in the case of chlamydia disease with CRAS are presented in table 1. As can be seen in practically healthy individuals, the amount of IgA and IgG in the PC, as well as the value of Csb. much lower than in patients with chlamydia. At the same time, in practically healthy individuals, in comparison with patients with chlamydia with CRAS, levels of total calcium, sialic acids, levels of inorganic phosphorus, SigA, lysozyme, and alkaline phosphatase activity are increased in PC.

Table №1

Biochemical and immunological parameters of pancreatic cancer in patients with CRAS with chlamydia

PC indicators	Control group	Before treatment n = 20 (1st group)	After treatment	
			n = 10 (1 main group).	n = 10 (1 comparison group)
Alkaline phosphatase, mmol / hr	1,3 ± 0,03	0,8±0,06*	1,3±0,02*	1,01±0,24*
Sialic acids, units	6,8 ± 0,18	4,2±0,12*	6,3±0,08*	5,9±0,34*
Total Ca, mmol / L	4,97 ± 0,39	0,60±0,04*	4,86±0,06*	4,19±0,42*
Inorganic phosphorus, mol / L	8,44 ± 0,62	2,9±0,59*	8,8±0,99*	7,9±0,88*
IgA, g / l	0,08 ± 0,021	0,18±0,02*	0,09±0,01*	0,1±0,01*
IgG, g / l	0,1 ± 0,01	0,18±0,02*	0,98±0,02*	0,68±0,02*
Lysozyme,%	44,2 ± 2,4	10,42±0,42*	42,88±0,41*	40,22±0,42*
SIgA, g / l	0,40 ± 0,06	0,06±0,04*	0,44±0,04*	0,28±0,08*
Csb.	1,48 ± 0,20	5,43±0,02*	5,40±0,02*	4,14±0,02*

Appendix: * - statistically significant differences relative to control (p <0.05).

Table №2 shows the results of a study of some immunological and biochemical parameters of pancreatic cancer with CRAS and with ureaplasmosis before and after treatment.

Table №2

Biochemical and immunological parameters of pancreatic cancer in patients with CRAS with ureaplasmosis.

PC indicators	Control group (n = 20) (n = 20) group (n = 20)	Before treatment n	After treatment	
			n = 10 (1 main group).	n = 10 (1 comparison group)
Alkaline phosphatase, mmol / hr	1,3 ± 0,06	0,90 ± 0,02*	1,24 ± 0,02*	1,1 ± 0,04*

Sialic acids, units	7,0 ± 0,12	5,20 ± 0,28*	6,78 ± 0,48*	6,24 ± 0,38*
Total Ca, mmol / L	5,0 ± 0,88	1,26 ± 0,05*	4,86 ± 0,03*	4,0 ± 0,06*
Inorganic phosphorus, mol / L	8,14 ± 0,32	2,98 ± 0,11*	7,88 ± 0,22*	7,21 ± 0,44*
IgA, g / l	0,08 ± 0,006	0,20 ± 0,04*	0,07 ± 0,01*	0,06 ± 0,04*
IgG, g / l	0,10 ± 0,001	0,14 ± 0,002*	0,10 ± 0,009*	0,09 ± 0,001*
Lysozyme, %	45,4 ± 2,6	13,9 ± 0,59*	44,9 ± 0,59*	44,2 ± 0,78*
SIgA, g / l	0,33 ± 0,08	0,14 ± 0,06*	0,31 ± 0,02*	0,31 ± 0,88*
Csb.	1,56 ± 0,17	2,66 ± 0,46*	1,51 ± 0,16*	1,46 ± 0,42*

Appendix: * - statistically significant differences relative to control (p < 0.05).

Table №4 shows the results of a study of some immunological as well as biochemical parameters of the composition of the pancreatic cancer in case of mycoplasmosis disease in comparison with CG. In practically healthy patients, the levels of sialic acids, IgA and IgG, as well as the value of Kcb. in PC is much lower than in individuals with mycoplasmosis.

Analysis of the levels of total calcium, inorganic phosphorus, lysozyme and SigA, as well as the activity of alkaline phosphatase in the composition of the pancreas confirmed their decrease in patients with mycoplasmosis, compared with representatives of the CG.

Table №3

Biochemical and immunological parameters of pancreatic cancer in patients with CRAS with mycoplasma.

PC indicators	Control group (n = 20) (n = 20) group (n = 20)	Before treatment n = 20 (1st group) (1-я группа)	After treatment	
			n = 10 (1 main group).	n = 10 (1 comparison group)
Alkaline phosphatase, mmol / hr	1,2 ± 0,06	0,80 ± 0,02*	1,1 ± 0,02*	1,0 ± 0,08*
Sialic acids, units	6,6 ± 0,22	8,42 ± 0,04*	6,5 ± 0,12*	6,0 ± 0,24*
Total Ca, mmol / L	4,98 ± 0,40	0,68 ± 0,02*	4,52 ± 0,01*	4,22 ± 0,02*
Inorganic phosphorus, mol / L	8,22 ± 0,32	3,88 ± 0,34*	8,0 ± 0,39*	7,7 ± 0,19*
IgA, g / l	0,07 ± 0,008	0,14 ± 0,002*	0,07 ± 0,002*	0,06 ± 0,001*
IgG, g / l	0,08 ± 0,001	0,13 ± 0,004*	0,08 ± 0,002*	0,07 ± 0,004*
Lysozyme, %	44,2 ± 2,4	14,56 ± 0,24*	43,12 ± 0,31*	41,12 ± 0,28*
SIgA, g / l	0,32 ± 0,08	0,15 ± 0,004*	0,30 ± 0,002*	0,30 ± 0,008*
Csb.	1,54 ± 0,20	3,21 ± 0,18*	1,51 ± 0,03*	1,47 ± 0,06*

Appendix: * - statistically significant differences relative to control (p < 0.05).

The relationship between CRAS and inflammatory manifestations in the pathology of the urogenital system in patients with CRAS compared with group 2 (p ≤ 0.01), local clinical manifestations of the inflammatory process in the urogenital tract were detected; for example, during the study, pathogens of chlamydia were detected by PCR in 49.4 ± 4.68% of cases; of them, PCR - in 27.3% of cases of chlamydia were found in scrapings from cervix, ureaplasma urealitikum - in 57.4 ± 2.86% of cases; mycoplasma hominis in 46.2 ± 2.9% of cases detected. These quality results are repeated in the results with the mutual fund and ELISA methods.

Comparison of pathogens in cancer with detection in other biosubstrates, such as blood and scrapings of the epithelium before and after complex treatment, we obtained positive results (tables №. 2, 3, 4).

The results of the material in the table state that, in patients with CRAS, chlamydia trachomatis, ureaplasma urealitikum, and mycoplasma hominis are significantly more often found in scrapings of the epithelium as compared with PC (Table №. 5).

Table №. 4.

The causative agents of the urinary tract infection in CRAS in biosubstrates by PCR, culture and PIF before and after complex treatment.

Method	Bio Substrate	Chlamydia Trachomatis		Mycoplasma Hominis		Ureaplasma urealitikum	
		+*	-**	+	-	+	-
PCR n-120	Epithelium scraping	100%	0%	100%	0%	100%	0%
	Blood	78±4,47%	22±4,2%	81,2±3,7%	18,8±5,7%	76±4,3%	23±6,3%
	Oral fluid	82±3,2%	17±7,8%	90,8±4,7%	9,9±2,8%	80±5,4%	20±1,4%
Sowing n-120	Epithelium scraping	-	-	100%	0%	90±4,9%	10±2,9%
	Oral fluid	-	-	89,1±6,2%	10,9±5%	82±4,9%	18±4,9%
Mutual fund n-120	Epithelium scraping	84±4,0%	16±2,8%	-	-	79±6,0%	21±2,0%
	Oral fluid	62±6,4%	33±4,5%	-	-	66±4,8%	33±3,9%
After treatment. (1-main group)							
PCR n-60	Comparison with before treatment	*** «+++»	*** «+++» - отрицательный	*** «+++»	*** «+++»	*** «+++»	*** «+++»
	Epithelium scraping	12,4±1,8	0%	6,8±0,84	0%	0%	0%
	Blood	14±1,44%	85±2,4%	9,4±1,4%	81±1,5%	6±1,2%	94±3,3%
Sowing n-60	Oral fluid	2,2±0,8	97±1,6%	2,8±0,7%	97±1,2%	11±1,4%	88±2,4%
	Epithelium scraping	-	-	11±1,1	88±0,8%	10±1,1%	88,9±2%
Mutual fund n-60	Oral fluid	-	-	2,1±1,1%	88±1%	2±1,1%	81,9±1,1
	Epithelium scraping	4±0,8%	95±1,8%	-	-	7±1,6%	92±3,0%
Mutual fund n-60	Oral fluid	2±1,4%	88±1,2%	-	-	6,2±1,8%	93±1,9%
	After treatment. (1 comparative group)						
PCR n-60	Epithelium scraping	18,8±1,86	0%	12,4±2,08	0%	0%	0%
	Blood	18±2,67%	88±1,4%	13,2±2,9%	86,8±1,7%	16±4,3%	83±1,3%
	Oral fluid	10±1,3%	89±1,4%	9,4±2,2%	90±1,1%	18±3,4%	82±2,6%
Sowing n-60	Epithelium scraping	-	-	14±0,6	85±2,8%	19±3,2%	80±0,9%
	Oral fluid	-	-	19,1±2,2%	80,9±2%	8±1,9%	82±1,1%
Mutual fund n-60	Epithelium scraping	14±2%	86±1,2%	-	-	9±1,0%	81±4,0%
	Oral fluid	6±0,4%	93,9±1,5%	-	-	16±3,8%	83±2,4%

Before treatment: * "+" - a positive result; ** "-" - negative result. After treatment: *** "++" - a positive result; **** "--" - negative result.

The results of the study of leukocytes, lymphocytes, monocytes, segamenuclear and polymyocadic neutrophils, eosonophils, B-lymphocytes and NST test parameters are shown in table №. 6.

Table №. 5.

Examined patients with CRAS and the focus of infection of the urinary tract (M ± m in %).

№	Biosubstrates (Shelter)	Amount		
		Before treatment n=120	After treatment	
			n = 60 (1st basic group)	n = 60 (1st comparative group)
1	White blood cell count (normal: 4-9 × 10 ⁹ / l)	5,8±0,28* (p<0,05)	7,8±0,48*	7,0±0,98*
2	Lymphocyte count normal: 19-37%)	34,0±0,42* (p<0,05)	30±0,92 (p<0,05)	30,4±0,22 (p<0,05)
3	Monocyte count (normal: 3-11%)	5,6±0,64 (p<0,05)	24,0±0,92*	20,8±0,94*
4	The number of segmented neutrophils (normal: 47-72%)	68,4±1,24* (p<0,05)	(p<0,05)	(p<0,05)
5	The number of stab neutrophils (normal: 1-6%)	2,32±0,62* (p<0,05)	5,8±0,94	4,6±0,44
6	The number of eosinophils (normal: 0.5-6%)	1,9±0,44* (p<0,05)	(p<0,05)	(p<0,05)
7	The number of b-lymphocytes (normal: 15-35%)	14,6±0,45* (p<0,05)	38,8±1,04*	18,8±1*
8	HCT Test Indicators (normal: 40-80%)	12,6±0,85* (p<0,05)	(p<0,05)	(p<0,05)

Appendix: * - statistically significant differences include. normal (p <0.05);

** - statistically significant differences relative to the control group (p <0.05).

The results of leukocytes and lymphocytes in the peripheral blood revealed an increase in their number in the examined groups of patients compared with CG. The severity of leukocytosis in patients with chronic angioplasty and urinary tract infection in most cases was associated with somatic pathologies. These results mean that leukocytosis and lymphocytosis in patients of the 1st group examined, in contrast to CG and patients with a cured urogenital infection without relapses and without CRAS.

In the peripheral blood in patients with CRAS, an increased percentage of monocytes was found or approaching the upper limit of the norm, which may also indirectly indicate the presence of pathology, but so far in the stage of compensation due to the reserve capabilities of the body. Significant differences in indices (p <0.01) were found in the number of stab neutrophils.

Thus, we revealed signs of the presence of chronic inflammatory processes already at this stage of immunological studies in patients with CRAS and a chronic infectious tract of the genitourinary tract.

According to our data, a chronic inflammatory process associated with the presence of opportunistic pathogens in the OC and in the genitourinary tract can develop in patients with CRAS and the site of infection of the genitourinary tract. The results obtained indicate that in patients with CRAS on the background of CKD, signs of local immunodeficiency were detected, which is largely determined by the place and prevalence of inflammation. In this case, no dependence on the specific causative agent of the infection in the path of the genitourinary tract was revealed.

The amount of IgG in patients with CRAS on the background of pathology of the genitourinary tract was 11.2 ± 0.16 g / l compared with CG: 12.8 ± 0.4 g / l (normal: 7.5-15.45 g / l); the IgA content in the 1st group of patients was 2.45 ± 0.48 g / l compared with a CG of 1.9 ± 0.08 g / l (normal: 1.25-2.5 g / l).

Thus, in the majority of patients with CRAS and foci of infection of the genitourinary tract, we observed immunological signs of exacerbated chronic inflammation. In addition, the prevalence and severity of allergic and autoimmune manifestations in these groups was also significantly higher (p <0.001), compared with CG.

V. Conclusion

The use of complex treatment included preparations of antihistamines, sedatives, multivitamin preparations and polyoxidonium, in local treatment on OF phytotherapy rinses OF with “Parsley juices” and “Clove essential oil” in problem areas of SOPR in patients of the first group of patients examined with CRAS with the presence of infectious pathology of the genitourinary system in complex treatment turned out to be the most effective compared with the treatment regimens used in the comparative group I and group II.

- In patients with CRAS in the presence of an infectious pathology of the genitourinary system, the following clinical manifestations are significantly more often (p <0.1.±0.001): CRAS, Mikulich aphthosis - 75%, Setten

apthosis - 25%, regional lymphadenitis (100%), the simultaneous appearance of aphthae in different areas SOPR (62%), swelling of SOPR (54%), a high level of intensity of tooth decay KPU - 14.61 ± 0.8 ; OHI-S index 1.96 ± 0.06 ; KPI - $1.68 \pm 0,1$.

- In patients with CRAS in the presence of an infectious pathology of the genitourinary system, relapse of CRAS, which has a longer and more severe course, with a brighter clinic and significantly worse treatment, is significantly more frequent ($p < 0.001$).

- In the presence of CRAS, bacteria predominate (68%), viruses are less common (55%). The most frequently detected were Chlamydia trachomatis (73%), Mycoplasma hominis (68%), Ureaplasma urealyticum (56%), Herpes simplex virus (57%), Papillomavirus hominis (23%), Cytomegalovirus hominis (17.6%). However, when immunostimulating and anti-inflammatory and antiviral phytotherapeutic treatments were included in the course of treatment, significantly more effective ($p < 0.001$) results (from 85-95%) were noted.

- With CRAS and an infection of the genitourinary system, immunological signs of exacerbation of chronic inflammation were detected. The main pathogenetic factor in the recurrence of infection in CRAS is immunodeficiency of T-cell and B-cell units, which has individual characteristics and a significant scatter in each patient with CRAS.

- Etiopathogenetic therapy; complex treatment - preparations of antihistamines, sedatives, multivitamin preparations and polyoxidonium, in local treatment for OF phytotherapy rinses OF with "Parsley juices" and "Clove essential oil", it is effective for 2-5 days, significantly ($p < 0.01$) reduces relapse rate (3%), does not cause adverse and allergic reactions (0%).

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